

After Constantine

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AC

STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

Orthodox Academy of Crete

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AC

Constantine the Great by *Chrzya Sakel*

THE METAPHORS OF MOTION IN ATHANASIUS' ACCOUNT OF IDOLATRY*

Viacheslav V. Lytvynenko**

This study focuses on Athanasius' account of idolatry in his double treatise *Contra Gentes* and *De Incarnatione Verbi*. It seeks to show the importance of this topic within Athanasius' theological framework by drawing the links with creation, fall, and incarnation as the central themes of this writing. The author suggests that a helpful way to identify such links is by looking into Athanasius' use of metaphors of motion. Therefore, the bulk of the article examines the way in which these metaphors are used to explain the origin of idolatry and the solution to the problem of pagan worship in *Contra Gentes*, and it also explores the key role of the incarnation in *De Incarnatione*. The author argues that Athanasius' description of humanity's movement to God by means of the soul, creation, and Scriptures in *Contra Gentes* is best understood as stressing the effectiveness of the incarnation in *De Incarnatione* rather than as standing in tension or contradicting it.

Keywords: Athanasius, double treatise, idolatry, metaphors, movement, upward, downward, fall, incarnation, soul, creation, Scripture.

When we read Athanasius' double treatise *Contra Gentes* and *De Incarnatione*, we often focus on the topics of creation, fall, and incarnation. We rarely read it to see what Athanasius has to say about idols. Yet a closer look into this work shows that this topic takes up a surprisingly large amount of space. Athanasius spends twenty-three chapters (7–29) out of forty-seven for a detailed discussion of it in *Contra Gentes*, and he addresses it again in *De Incarnatione* (chs. 11–15, 18, 20–21, 30–32, 37, 40, 43, 45–53, 55), where idolatry is covered less directly but still holding a fair bit of attention in twenty-three chapters out of fifty-seven. In fact, this topic is so interwoven with all the other major themes of the treatise that one could reasonably argue that a failure to give it proper attention can leave one with an inadequate understanding of Athanasius' thought. At the time when he wrote

this work,[1] the gods of Roman Egypt were still making a profound impression on people, [2] and it is not without a reason that Athanasius ends his treatise specifically with a note on the triumph of Christianity over idols: *So, after what has been said above, this you must learn and consider as the principle of what remains unmentioned, and marvel at greatly: that when the Saviour came, idolatry no more increased, but even that which existed is diminishing and gradually ceasing. The wisdom of the Greeks no longer prosper, but even that which does exist is now disappearing. And the demons no longer deceive with phantasies and oracles and magic, but as soon as they dare and try they are put to shame by the sign of the cross. To sum up, see how the teaching of the Saviour increases everywhere, while all idolatry and all opposition to the faith of Christ day by day diminish and weaken and fall.[3]*

Another curious aspect that shows up with a closer look into Athanasius' account of idolatry is his frequent use of the metaphors of motion. He puts them into service while discussing the origin of idolatry and offering his refutations of pagan cults throughout the double treatise. So, what is the theological function of these metaphors and how do they help Athanasius to make his points? In this article, I am going to explore this in several ways. First, I will ask how Athanasius employs the metaphors of motion in *Contra Gentes* (henceforth CG) to explain why people began substituting the true God for pagan deities. Second, I will discuss the solution he offers in this text to the problem of idol worship by calling the pagans to reverse their downward movement to the upward one by means of the soul, creation, and Scriptures. Finally, I will suggest that zooming in on these metaphors of movement can help us sharpen Athanasius' answer to the "why" question of the incarnation in the second part of his treatise *De Incarnation Verbi* (henceforth De Inc.), to be considered at the end of this study.

Before addressing the subject of idolatry in CG 7, Athanasius gives a brief account of humanity as it was originally created and then fell into sin. Two major ideas that one immediately sees here are "remaining" and "direction." In creation, humanity was made to "rejoice and converse with God, living an idyllic and truly blessed and immortal life,"[4] and "such did he [the Creator] wish it to remain (μένειν)."[5] Yet what led humanity to sin was the radical change of direction, as Athanasius puts it:

But men, contemptuous of the better things and shrinking from their apprehension, sought rather what was closer to themselves – and what was closer to them was the body and its sensations. So they turned their minds away (ἀπέστησαν ἑαυτῶν τὸν νοῦν) from intelligible reality and began to consider themselves. And by considering themselves and cleaving to the body and the other senses, deceived as it were in their own interests, they fell into selfish desires and preferred their own good to the contemplation of the divine. [6]

Out of this idea of the wrong direction in which humanity stopped being focused on God and became concentrated on self, Athanasius brings a wide variety of metaphors of motion to depict the disastrous change that happened to humanity after the fall and the way it led people to make idols and worship them. To explain how exactly the first people "fell into (καταβεγήκασιν) the folly of idols,"[7] he begins with two illustrations in chs. 8 and 9, where his language is dominated with metaphors of motion. In CG 7.14–32, Athanasius writes:

Evil neither came from God nor was in God, nor did it exist in the beginning, nor has it any independent reality. But men, rejecting the notion of the good, began to think up for themselves (φαντασίας ἑαυτοῖς ἐπινοεῖν ἤρξαντο) and invent objects which do not exist (τὰ οὐκ ὄντα) as the fancy struck them. For they were like someone who closes his eyes when the sun is shining and all the earth is illuminated by its light, and imagines darkness which does not exist (οὐκ ὄντος), and then wanders about missing his way as if in the dark, often falling and stumbling over precipices (ὡς ἐν σκότει πλανώμενος περιπατῆ, πολλάκις πίπτων καὶ κατὰ κρημνῶν ὑπάγων), thinking it was not light but dark, for he thinks he is looking, but does not see at all. In similar fashion the soul of men, shutting the eye through which it could see God, imagined evil (κακὰ ἐπενόησεν), and moving therein (ἐν οἷς κινουμένη) did not realize that, although it thought it was acting, it did nothing at all, for it was inventing non-existent things (τὰ οὐκ ὄντα). And it did not remain (ἔμεινεν) as it had been made but appeared such as it had defiled itself. For it was created to see God and be enlightened by him; but instead of God it pursued (ἔζητήσεν) corruptible things and darkness, as the Spirit says somewhere in the Scriptures: "God made man upright, but they sought many notions" (Eccles. 7.30). In this way the invention and notion of evil occurred to men and was limned from the beginning.[8] Several things are noteworthy in this passage. First, Athanasius links the origin of idolatry to the choice of humanity not to remain as it was originally made. It was created to contemplate

God but chose to reject him and pursue things that were not divine. Second, Athanasius identifies this moment of change as the reason why people began to imagine evil – which could not originate from God – and eventually make idols. Since idols are part of human evil imagination, they are rightly called “non-existent things” or “objects which do not exist,” just as evil itself “has no independent reality.” Lastly, Athanasius uses a number of metaphors of motion to describe what happened to people after the fall. He illustrates their fallen condition by comparing them to a person who decides to close his eyes, and as a result such a person is left to “wander around” (πλανώμενος περιπατῆ), often “falling” (πίπτων), and “stumbling over steep places” (κατὰ κρημνῶν ὑπάγων). Instead of remaining as it was made (οὐχ ὅποια γέγονε, τοιαύτη καὶ ἔμεινε), mankind imagined evil and moved in it (τὰ κακὰ ἐπενόησεν, ἐν οἷς κινουμένη).

In the next chapter, Athanasius reiterates his claim that “evil is the prime cause of idolatry”[9] and then offers another example to illustrate the way humanity began “to regress (ἐξάγειν) to worse things”[10] after the fall, creating idols with no reality in them. Here the metaphors of movement abound again:

If someone falls into (καταδύς) an abyss and no longer sees the light nor what is visible in the light because his eyes are pointed downwards (πρὸς τὸ κάτω) and the water is pouring over him, being aware only of what is in the abyss, he thinks there is nothing except that, and that what he perceives are the most important entities. In similar fashion men of old foolishly sank (καταδύντες) to the desires and fantasies of the body and, forgetting their conception and idea of God, with feeble reasoning – or rather irrationally – represented phenomena as gods and glorified creation instead of the creator, deifying its works rather than their cause and fashioner and lord, God. And as, in the above example of those who fell into (καταδυόμενοι) the abyss, the deeper they descend (ἐπικαταβαίνουσι) the greater is the darkness, so also was the case with the race of men. For they did not merely adhere to idolatry or remain (διέμειναν) where they had begun, but the longer they spent in their original errors, the more they invented ever new superstitions. And unsated

with the original evils they glutted themselves with others, progressing (προκόπτοντες) in iniquity and extending (ἐπεκτείνοντες) their impiety still further. To this the Divine Scripture bears witness, saying: “When the impious man has descended into the abyss of evil he is disdainful” (Prov. 18.3)[11]

In a very Platonic fashion,[12] Athanasius describes a person who finds himself in the pit, where he cannot see the true reality, and therefore thinks that the only real things that exist are the ones he perceives. Such a person is depicted as having fallen into (καταδύς) the pit – with his eyes turned downward (πρὸς τὸ κάτω) – and fallen humanity is like that person. It moves in a descending direction, and to describe this Athanasius talks about the first people who “foolishly sank (καταδύντες) to the desires and fantasies of the body” and “the deeper they descended (καταδυόμενοι) the greater was the darkness.” Instead of remaining (διέμειναν), they “progressed (προκόπτοντες) in iniquity and extended (ἐπεκτείνοντες) their impiety still further,” thus inventing new superstitions and new gods.

Clearly, the sort of movement we observe in chs. 7 and 8 of *Contra Gentes* has a negative sense. Athanasius describes the fallen humanity with metaphors of downward motion that imply either disorder (such as wandering around, stumbling, and falling) or regress (descending deeper and deeper into the pit and darkness), and the end result of this movement is the invention of idols. In the rest of his account of idolatry, Athanasius reinforces this idea of downward movement in three other episodes.

The first episode comes in ch. 9, where we have a discussion of various developments of idolatry. Here Athanasius talks about people’s desire to make their own gods out of celestial bodies, objects of nature, made-up creatures, personified lusts, as well as living and dead men. Tracing the roots of this desire for making gods and worshipping them, he argues that it began once humanity “turned from the true and only real

God.”[13] In describing this turn from God to pagan deification, he uses a number of metaphors of downward motion as a clearly negative thing:

Once men’s minds had turned away (ἀπεπήδησεν) from God, they became degraded (καταβαίνοντες) in their thoughts and reasonings, and paid the honour due to God first to heaven and the sun and moon and stars, thinking them not only to be gods but also the causes of things other than themselves. Then, descending lower (ἐπικαταβαίνοντες) in their obscure arguments, they called the ether and the air and the things in the air gods. Advancing further (προβαίνοντες) in their evil thoughts, they now praised the elements and the principles of the composition of bodies – the warm and cold, dry and wet – as gods. Like those who have fallen right down (πεσόντες) and crawl on the earth as snails on the ground, these most impious of men, in their descent from the contemplation of God (πεσόντες καὶ καταπεσόντες ἀπὸ τῆς περὶ Θεοῦ φαντασίας), then raised to divine status even men and images of men, some while still alive, and others after their death.[14]

In this passage, Athanasius repeatedly emphasizes the downward movement of humanity and the way it drove people to idolatry. Thus, he speaks of ancient people as “going lower in their thoughts and reasonings” (καταβαίνοντες ταῖς ἐννοίαις καὶ τοῖς λογισμοῖς) to explain their desire to honor celestial entities. He also depicts them as “descending yet lower in their obscure arguments” (ἐπικαταβαίνοντες τοῖς σκοτεινοῖς λογισμοῖς), when they started to treat the ether and the air as gods. Finally, describing this degradation even further, Athanasius stresses again that “they were falling lower and lower from the contemplation of God” (πεσόντες καὶ καταπεσόντες ἀπὸ τῆς περὶ Θεοῦ φαντασίας) as they set up men, beasts, creeping creatures, and rocks as their gods. The picture we gain here is one of gradual movement that put people one step down each time they added a new deity to their list. In fact, this descent from God to idolatry was so humiliating that Athanasius compares humanity with snails: “Like those who have fallen right down (πεσόντες) and crawl on the earth as snails on the ground.”

In chs. 19 and 23 of *Contra Gentes*, we have two other episodes where Athanasius employs the metaphors of downward motion for his account of idolatry. In the first of them, he speaks of people as “having fallen into the unreasonableness of their passions and pleasures” (εἰς γὰρ τὴν τῶν παθῶν καὶ ἡδονῶν ἀλογίαν πεσόντες)[15] and describes the invention of idols as a process of “going down to the making of gods” (ἐπὶ τὴν τοιαύτην θεοπλασίαν κατέπεσον).[16] Athanasius concludes that “having fallen (πεσόντες) [...], they wallow (κυλίνονται) thus in these pleasures and model God the Father of the Word in animal form.”[17] In the final episode, Athanasius talks about the variety of pagan cults and all sorts of disagreements among them. Thus, the Phoenicians do not recognize the gods of the Egyptians, and the Egyptians do not recognize the gods of the Phoenicians. A great deal of variety and conflict concerning gods is also found among the Scythians, Persians, Syrians, Pelasgians, Thracians, Thebans, Indians, Arabs, Cilicians, Cappadocians, Bithynians, and Armenians. According to Athanasius, this confusion about multiple gods in different places is the direct result of the rejection of the one true God, which he describes in terms of the downward motion:

For having fallen from (ἐκπεσόντες) the contemplation of the one God they have come down (καταπεπτώκασι) to many various cults; since they turned from (ἀποστραφέντες) the true Word of the Father, Christ the Saviour of all, it is right that their minds should be wandering in many directions (εἰκότως εἰς πολλὰ τὴν διάνοιαν ἔχουσι ῥεμβομένην). Just as those who turn away from (ἀποστραφέντες) the sun to dwell in the shade circle around in many pathless tracks (πολλὰς ἀνόδους κυκλεύουσιν ὁδοῦς), not seeing those at hand but imagining the absent to be present, and “seeing do not see” (Matt. 13.13), in the same way those who have turned from (ἀποστραφέντες) God and have darkened their souls, have their minds in a roving state (ῥεμβόμενον ἔχουσι τὸν νοῦ), and like drunken and blind men they imagine things which do not exist.[18]

People's turn from the contemplation of God and the following downward movement toward the invention of idols is presented here in three ways. First, their minds are said to be wandering in many directions (εἰς πολλὰ τὴν διάνοιαν ἔχουσι ῥεμβομένην); second, they are like those who circle around in many pathless ways (πολλὰς ἀνόδους κυκλεύουσιν ὁδοῦς), as if they were in dark places, away from the sun; and third, they are compared to a drunk whose mind is in a roving state (ῥεμβόμενον ἔχουσι τὸν νοῦ). As a result, they see what is not there and imagine things that are not true.

Thus, whatever metaphors Athanasius uses to describe the state of idolatrous pagans in these three episodes (whether falling, descending, wallowing, going in circles, or wandering around), and whatever comparisons he draws (whether snails who crawl down, or someone who sits in the dark, or a drunk who is not able to control his movements), the basic idea is very clear. Turning away from the true God set humanity on the downward movement, and the lower it went the more outrageous was its desire to make gods and worship them.

Although Athanasius ends his account of idolatry in ch. 29 of *Contra Gentes*, he briefly returns to this topic several times again in the rest of the treatise. To appreciate his thought about idolatry here, I suggest that it is best to read the remaining chapters as a call to reverse the downward movement to the upward one by contemplating God by means of three major ways – the soul (chs. 30–34), creation (chs. CG 35–45a), and Scriptures (chs. 45b–47). While interpreters generally agree on the importance of these means in *Contra Gentes*, there has been a question as to whether the human role in this part of the treatise may go against the divine action in *De Incarnatione*. In dealing with this issue, scholars have interpreted it as either a matter of conflicting anthropologies and views of salvation[19] or as a difference of emphases within a consistent narrative.[20]

The second of these views makes sense if we read the remaining chapters of *Contra Gentes* as an account of the general economy of God that reaches its peak with the incarnation of Christ in *De Incarnatione*. In this case, whether it is the power of the soul, the works of creation, or the revelation of the Scriptures, all three are given to humanity by God. None of them are supposed to work autonomously or by themselves. Each of their purposes is to serve as divine tools for reversing the downward movement of the fallen mankind to the upward trajectory, and the closer one gets to the topic of the incarnation, the more obvious become the limits of these other means. In what follows, I will briefly look into this framework and the way Athanasius deals with the problem of idolatry here.

Beginning in ch. 30 of *Contra Gentes*, Athanasius turns his attention to the soul and spends the next three chapters proving its existence and describing its functions. Defining the “road” (ἡ ὁδός) to God as that which is “within ourselves” (ἐν ἡμῖν), he identifies it with the soul and makes several statements about its faculty to lift us up to things divine. Thus, in CG 33, he compares the soul with the body and says that “while the body is lying motionless (μὴ κινουμένου) in bed as it were asleep in death, it [the soul] is awake according to its proper capacity and surpasses (ὑπερεκβαίνει) the nature of the body. As if abandoning the body, yet remaining in it, the soul pictures and contemplates things superterrestrial, often meeting saints and angels no longer in their earthly bodies”[21] Furthermore, he claims that pagans rejected God for their worship of idols precisely because they do not think they have a rational soul,[22] for by creating idols, they “act against reason and as if they had no soul.”[23] Therefore, the first step that can lead the pagans to the true God is their recognition of the soul, which Athanasius describes in terms of upward movement:

For just as they turned away (ἀπεστράφησαν) from God with their mind and invented gods from non-existent entities, so they can rise (ἀναβῆναι) towards God with the mind of their soul and again turn back (ἐπιστρέψαι) towards him. They can turn back (ἐπιστρέψαι) if they cast off the stain of all desire which they have put on, and wash themselves until they have eliminated every addition foreign to the soul and show it unadulterated, as it was made, in order that in this way they may be able to contemplate therewith the Word of the Father, in whose image they were made in the beginning. [24]

Here “turning away” (ἐπιστρέψαι) from idols and “rising up” (ἀναβῆναι) to God is that which takes place by contemplating him in the soul after it is cleansed and able to reflect its Creator. At the same time, Athanasius makes it clear that the soul is by no means a self-sufficient method of coming to God because of the soul’s created – and therefore limited – nature. For that reason, when the power of the soul does not succeed to accomplish its task, there is another means of coming to know the true God for the pagans, which is through the works of creation: “If this instruction on the part of the soul itself is not sufficient (μὴ ἀυτάρκης) because of external influences which disturb its mind and prevent it from seeing the better course, it is still possible to grasp knowledge about God from visible phenomena, since creation through its order and harmony, as it were in writing, indicates and proclaims its master and maker.”[25]

Athanasius discusses the theme of creation and its role in leading people to God in chs. 35–45. In the process, he identifies idolatry with polytheism and atheism,[26] and argues that the existing order and harmony of the universe should make the pagans “think that God is its leader and that he is one and not many.”[27] To believe in multiple gods and creators is wrong because the world “would have had its movements at variance and dissimilar to itself”[28] and there “would have been disorder and chaos in the universe.”[29] Thus, with creation being another important means of knowing God within the scope of the divine economy, it is no surprise that Athanasius describes a reflection about it in terms of an upward paradigm: “As by looking

up to heaven (ἀναβλέψαντας) and seeing its order and the light of the stars one can form an idea (ἐνθυμεῖσθαι) of the Word who sets their order, so when thinking of the Word of God one must also think of his Father, God, from whom he proceeds and is therefore rightly called the interpreter and messenger of his Father.”[30]

However, just like the soul, creation has its limits. God created it “out of nothing” (ἐξ οὐκ ὄντων), [31] and therefore, it is “unstable, and weak, and mortal when considered by itself.”[32] For that reason, when the works of creation fail to lead a pagan to God, there is also the revelation of Scriptures, which Athanasius discusses in the final chapters of *Contra Gentes*. The Scriptures are superior both to the soul and creation because they “preach more clearly and forcefully” (φανερώτερον καὶ κατὰ μείζον κηρύττει)[33] about God. Athanasius sums up his thought about the Scriptures in ch. 45, and as before, idolatry is described here in terms of the wrong direction. It is a “turning away” (ἀποστραφεῖς) from the true God to the deification of non-existing things, of which the Scriptures warned the Jews from the very beginning:

For the Jewish people had previously had fuller teaching, since they had knowledge of God not only from the works of creation but also from the Divine Scriptures. And Scripture gives men a general dissuasion from the error of idolatry and irrational imaginings in these words: “You will have no other gods except me” (Ex. 20.3). It is not as if there were other gods that Scripture forbids men to have them, but lest anyone, turning away from (ἀποστραφεῖς) the true God, should begin to deify for himself non-existent things, such as are the spurious gods mentioned and indicated by the prophets and historians.[34]

The fact that Athanasius treats the soul, creation, and Scriptures before the subject of the incarnation suggests, in my opinion, that he intended for the latter to appear as the peak of God’s economy of salvation. He devotes the entire treatise of *De Incarnatione* to the discussion of the incarnation, yet even here he spends a considerable space talking about idolatry. In the remaining part of this article, I will briefly consider two major ways

in which the downward movement of God represented in Christ's incarnation deals with idolatry here. While they are closely interconnected, each of them adds its own aspect important for gaining a fuller picture of why incarnation was needed.

The first way is epistemological. In *De Inc.* 14, Athanasius poses the following question: "But whose task was it to teach the world about the Father after the madness of idolatry and impiety got hold of the world and knowledge of God was hidden?"[35] To answer it, he resorts to the incarnation of Christ and the way it re-directs humanity upward by giving them a new form of revelation:

For men had neglected it [i.e., the works of creation] previously, and their eyes were no longer directed upwards (ἄνω) but downwards (κάτω). So as it was right for him to wish to be of help to men, he came as a man and took to himself a body like theirs of humble origin – I mean through the works of the body – in order that those who were unwilling to know him by his providence and government of the universe, yet by the works done through the body might know the Word of God who was in the body, and through him the Father.[36]

Athanasius' expression "their eyes were no longer directed upwards (ἄνω) but downwards (κάτω)" in this passage reminds us of his metaphors of motion in CG 7.14–32, where he compared the fallen men to those who closed their eyes, and as a result were left to wander around, fall, and stumble. This time, the problem of closed eyes has become one of misdirected vision and to deal with it, the works of Christ provide the knowledge about God that humanity could not attain on its own, just by looking at creation.

The second way how incarnation deals with idolatry, according to Athanasius, is by destroying the demons. The victory of Christ over them overthrows the idols and persuades the pagans to leave their cults. In fact, the triumph of Christianity over paganism is so remarkable that "at the coming of the Saviour all nations everywhere have begun to know God." [37] In *De Inc.* 15.25–37, the incarnation of Christ and his resurrection are specifically described as that which overcomes the

demons, brings superior knowledge of God, and lifts men upward (αὐτοὺς ἀναγάγη) like no other means available to humanity before:

But if they were prejudiced for the demons, yet when they saw them being put to flight by the Lord, they recognized that only he was the Word of God and that the demons were not gods. And if their minds were by then fixed on the dead, so that they worshipped the heroes and those said to be gods by the poets, yet when they saw the resurrection of the Saviour they confessed that the former were false, and that only the Word of the Father was the true Lord, he who has power over death. For this reason he was born and appeared as a man and died and rose again, weakening and overshadowing by his own works those of all men who ever existed, in order that from wherever men were attracted he might lift them up (ἐκεῖθεν αὐτοὺς ἀναγάγη) and teach them his true Father, as he himself says: "I have come to save and find that which was lost" (Luke 19.10).[38]

The way incarnation reverses the downward trajectory in which the fallen mankind has moved to an upward one is most clearly articulated ten chapters later in *De Inc.* 25. Here the coming of Christ opens the way to heaven that was blocked by the demons in the previous times, and Athanasius uses numerous metaphors of motion to make his point:

In addition, if the enemy of our race, the devil, having fallen (ἐκπεσὼν) from heaven moves around in this lower atmosphere (περὶ τὸν ἀέρα τὸν ὧδε κάτω πλανᾶται), and lording it here over his fellow demons in disobedience, through them works vain fancies to cheat men and tries to prevent them from rising upwards (τοῖς ἀνερχομένοις), the Apostle speaks of this also: "According to the ruler of the power of the air, who now works in the sons of disobedience" (Eph. 2.2). But the Lord came to overthrow (καταβάλη) the devil, purify the air, and open for us the way up to heaven (ὁδοποίησεν ἡμῖν τὴν εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον), as the Apostle said, through the veil, that is, his flesh (Heb 10.20). This had to be effected by death, and by what other death would these things have been accomplished save by that which takes place in the air, I mean the cross? For only he who expires on the cross dies in the air. So it was right for the Lord to endure it. For being raised up (ὑψωθεῖς) in this way he purified the air from the wiles of the devil and all the demons, saying: "I saw Satan falling (πεσόντα) as lightning" (Luke 10.18). And he reopened the way up to heaven (εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον ὁδοποιῶν ἐνεκαίνισεν), saying again: "Lift up (Ἄρατε) your gates, princes, and be

raised, (ἐπάρθητε) everlasting gates” (Ps. 23.7). For it was not the Word himself who needed the gates to be opened (ἀνοίξεως), since he is Lord of all, nor was any part of creation closed to its Maker; but we were those who needed it, whom he bore up through his own body (οὐς ἀνέφερεν αὐτὸς διὰ τοῦ ἰδίου σώματος αὐτοῦ). For as he offered it to death on behalf of all, so through it again he opened the way up to heaven (πάλιν ὠδοποίησε τὴν εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον).[39]

Athanasius describes the devil as the one who “wanders about our lower atmosphere” (περὶ τὸν ἄερα τὸν ὧδε κάτω πλανᾶται), trying to hinder those who are going up (τοῖς ἀνερχομένοις). Such efforts of the devil were overturned by the incarnation of Christ and his death on the cross, and Athanasius describes the fruits of Christ’s work in two ways. First, it “cleansed the air” and “opened the way up to heaven” (ὀδοποίησι ἡμῖν τὴν εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον), which Athanasius reiterates three more times in this passage. He says that Christ “reopened the way up to heaven” (εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον ὀδοποιῶν ἐνεκαίνιζε) and that we needed the gates of heaven to “be opened” (ἀνοίξεως) for us; and he repeats that his death on behalf of all was that which “again opened the way up to heaven” (πάλιν ὠδοποίησε τὴν εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον). Second, Christ bore us up through his own body (οὐς ἀνέφερεν αὐτὸς διὰ τοῦ ἰδίου σώματος αὐτοῦ), meaning that instead of leaving us with the task of rising to God, he accomplished it for us by carrying us up through his own body.[40] Accordingly, he opened the way for us to heaven and brought us up to God through himself.

Of course, Athanasius spends his entire career as a bishop of the Alexandrian church pondering upon these ideas and developing them further in his later writings. However, the origin of these ideas belongs to his apologetic work of refuting paganism and the worship of idols. Our close look into this hopefully makes it clear that the problem of idolatry is important enough for Athanasius that he spends almost half of *Contra Gentes* in order to deal with it, and he carries this topic over to *De*

Incarnatione for additional reflection. As a result, one cannot have a fuller picture of what Athanasius writes about creation, fall, and incarnation – the topics we normally look for in the double treatise – without giving proper attention to what he says about the pagan worship of idols.

Similarly, one cannot appreciate Athanasius’ account of idolatry sufficiently without looking into the metaphors of motion placed throughout the treatise. They describe the fall and the incarnation and also form an essential part of how Athanasius sees the solution to the problem of idolatry. Here the idea of reversing the downward movement of the fallen mankind to the upward one by means of the soul, creation, and Scriptures is the key to understanding why the work of Christ was needed. Being the most superior way of re-directing man to God, it did what humanity could not accomplish through the other means available before. Most importantly, it destroyed the demons who were blocking the way to God, re-opened the doors to heaven, and ultimately brought humanity to God.

Notes

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[1]Scholars disagree on whether this treatise was written before the outbreak of the Arian controversy in A.D. 318 or 319, or much later when the controversy already intensified in A.D. 350. The consensus date is A.D. 335 or 336. For a helpful summary of opinions, see Leemans 2000, pp. 132–135.

[2] Frankfurter 2017, esp. pp. 233–255.

[3] Athanasius, *De Inc.* 55.1–11 (Thomson 1971, pp. 269–270): "Τοῦτο οὖν μετὰ τὰ προειρημένα καταμαθεῖν σε ἄξιόν ἐστιν καὶ ὡς ἀρχὴν τῶν μὴ λεχθέντων θέσθαι, καὶ θαυμάσαι λίαν ὅτι τοῦ Σωτῆρος ἐπιδημήσαντος οὐκ ἔτι μὲν ἠὔξησεν ἡ εἰδωλολατρία, καὶ ἡ οὐσα δὲ ἐλαττοῦται, καὶ κατ' ὀλίγον παύεται· καὶ οὐκ ἔτι μὲν ἡ Ἑλλήνων σοφία προκόπτει, καὶ ἡ οὐσα δὲ λοιπὸν ἀφανίζεται· καὶ δαίμονες μὲν οὐκ ἔτι φαντασίαις καὶ μαντείαις καὶ μαγείαις ἀπατῶσι, μόνον δὲ τολμῶντες καὶ ἐπιχειροῦντες κατασχύνονται τῷ σημείῳ τοῦ σταυροῦ. Καὶ συλλήβδην εἰπεῖν, θεώρει πῶς ἡ μὲν τοῦ Σωτῆρος διδασκαλία πανταχοῦ αὔξει· πᾶσα δὲ εἰδωλολατρία καὶ πάντα τὰ ἐναντιούμενα τῇ Χριστοῦ πίστει καθ' ἡμέραν ἐλαττοῦται καὶ ἐξασθενεῖ καὶ πίπτει."

[4] *Ibid.*, CG 2.14–15 (Thomson 1971, pp. 6–7): "Ἀγάλληται καὶ συνομιλῆ τῷ Θεῷ, ζῶν τὸν ἀπήμονα καὶ μακάριον ὄντως ἀθάνατον βίον."

[5] *Ibid.*, CG 3.1–2 (Thomson 1971, pp. 8–9): "Καὶ μένειν ἠθέλησεν."

[6] *Ibid.*, CG 3.2–9 (Thomson 1971, pp. 8–9): "Οἱ δὲ ἄνθρωποι, κατολιγώρησαντες τῶν κρειπτόνων, καὶ ὀκνήσαντες περὶ τὴν τούτων κατάληψιν, τὰ ἐγγυτέρω μᾶλλον ἑαυτῶν ἐζήτησαν, ἐγγύτερα δὲ τούτοις ἦν τὸ σῶμα, καὶ αἱ τούτου αἰσθήσεις. ὅθεν τῶν μὲν νοητῶν ἀπέστησαν ἑαυτῶν τὸν νοῦν, ἑαυτοὺς δὲ κατανοεῖν ἤρξαντο. ἑαυτοὺς δὲ κατανοοῦντες, καὶ τοῦ τε σώματος καὶ τῶν ἄλλων αἰσθητῶν ἀντιλαμβανόμενοι, καὶ ὡς ἐν ἰδίῳ ἀπατῶμενοι, εἰς ἑαυτῶν ἐπιθυμίαν ἔπεσαν, τὰ ἴδια προτιμήσαντες τῆς πρὸς τὰ θεῖα θεωρίας."

[7] *Ibid.*, CG 7.33 (Thomson 1971, pp. 18–19): "Εἰς τὴν τῶν εἰδώλων μανίαν καταβεβήκασιν."

[8] *Ibid.*, CG 7.14–32 (Thomson 1971, pp. 18–19): "Τὸ κακὸν οὐ παρὰ Θεοῦ οὐδὲ ἐν Θεῷ οὔτε ἐξ ἀρχῆς γέγονεν, οὔτε οὐσία τίς ἐστιν αὐτοῦ. ἀλλὰ ἄνθρωποι κατὰ στέρησιν τῆς τοῦ καλοῦ φαντασίας ἑαυτοῖς ἐπινοεῖν ἤρξαντο καὶ ἀναπλάττειν τὰ οὐκ ὄντα, καὶ ἄπερ βούλονται. ὡς γὰρ ἂν τις ἡλίου φαίνοντος, καὶ πάσης τῆς γῆς τῷ φωτὶ τούτου καταλαμπομένης, καμμῶν τοὺς ὀφθαλμούς, σκότος ἑαυτῷ ἐπινοῆ οὐκ ὄντος σκότους, καὶ λοιπὸν ὡς ἐν σκότει πλανώμενος περιπατῆ, πολλακίς πίπτων καὶ κατὰ κρημνῶν ὑπάγων, νομίζων οὐκ εἶναι φῶς, ἀλλὰ σκότος· δοκῶν γὰρ βλέπειν, οὐδ' ὅλως ὄρα· οὕτω καὶ ἡ ψυχὴ τῶν ἀνθρώπων, καμμῶσα τὸν ὀφθαλμὸν δι' οὗ τὸν Θεὸν ὄρα δύναται, ἑαυτῇ τὰ κακὰ ἐπενόησεν, ἐν οἷς

κινουμένη, οὐκ οἶδεν ὅτι δοκοῦσά τι ποιεῖν, οὐδὲν ποιεῖ· τὰ οὐκ ὄντα γὰρ ἀναπλάττεται. καὶ οὐχ ὅποια γέγονε, τοιαύτη καὶ ἔμεινε· ἀλλ' ὅποιαν ἑαυτὴν ἐνέφυρε, τοιαύτη καὶ φαίνεται. γέγονε μὲν γὰρ εἰς τὸ ὄρα τὸν Θεὸν καὶ ὑπ' αὐτοῦ φωτίζεσθαι· αὕτη δὲ ἀντὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ τὰ φθαρτὰ καὶ τὸ σκότος ἐζήτησεν, ὡς που καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα ἐγγράφως φησὶν· "Ὁ Θεὸς τὸν ἄνθρωπον ἐποίησεν εὐθῆ· αὐτοὶ δὲ ἐζήτησαν λογισμοὺς πολλούς." κακίας δὲ οὖν εὔρεσις καὶ ἐπίνοια τοῖς ἀνθρώποις ἐξ ἀρχῆς οὕτω γέγονε καὶ πέπλαστα."

[9] *Ibid.*, CG 8.18–19 (Thomson 1971, pp. 20–21): "Προηγεῖται τοίνυν αἰτία τῆς εἰδωλολατρίας ἡ κακία (trans. mine)."

[10] *Ibid.*, CG 8.2 (Thomson 1971, pp. 20–21): "Εἰς τὰ χείρονα ἑαυτὴν ἐξάγειν ἤρξατο."

[11] *Ibid.*, CG 8.21–41 (Thomson 1971, pp. 20–23): "Οἷον δὲ εἴ τις, εἰς βυθὸν καταδύς, μηκέτι μὲν βλέπει τὸ φῶς, μηδὲ τὰ ἐν τῷ φωτὶ φαινόμενα, διὰ τὸ τῶν ὀφθαλμῶν αὐτοῦ πρὸς τὸ κάτω νεῦμα, καὶ τὴν τοῦ ὕδατος ἐπικειμένην ἐπίχυσιν αὐτῷ· μόνον δὲ τὰ ἐν τῷ βυθῷ αἰσθόμενος, νομίζει μηδὲν πλέον ἐκείνων εἶναι, ἀλλ' αὐτὰ τὰ φαινόμενα αὐτῷ τῶν ὄντων εἶναι τὰ κύρια· οὕτω καὶ οἱ πάλαι τῶν ἀνθρώπων παράφρονες, καταδύντες εἰς τὰς τῶν σαρκῶν ἐπιθυμίας καὶ φαντασίας, καὶ ἐπιλαθόμενοι τῆς περὶ Θεοῦ ἐννοίας καὶ δόξης, ἀμυδρῶ τῷ λογισμῷ, μᾶλλον δὲ ἀλογίᾳ χρῆσάμενοι, τὰ φαινόμενα θεοὺς ἀνετυπώσαντο, τὴν κτίσιν παρὰ τὸν κτίσαντα δοξάζοντες, καὶ τὰ ἔργα μᾶλλον ἐκθειάζοντες ἢ περὶ τὸν τούτων αἴτιον καὶ δημιουργὸν δεσπότην Θεόν. ὥσπερ δὲ κατὰ τὸ προλεχθὲν παράδειγμα, οἱ εἰς τὸν βυθὸν καταδυόμενοι, ὅσῳ μᾶλλον ἐπικαταβαίνουσι, τοσοῦτον εἰς τὰ σκοτεινότερα καὶ βαθύτερα ὀρμῶσιν· οὕτω καὶ τὸ τῶν ἀνθρώπων πέπονθε γένος. οὐ γὰρ ἀπλῆν ἔσχον τὴν εἰδωλολατρίαν, οὐδὲ ἀφ' ὧν ἤρξαντο ἐν τούτοις καὶ διέμειναν· ἀλλ' ὅσον τοῖς πρώτοις ἐνεχρόνιζον, τοσοῦτον ἑαυτοῖς καινότερας ἐφεύρισκον δεισιδαιμονίας· καὶ κόρον οὐ λαμβάνοντες τῶν πρώτων, ἄλλοις

πάλιν ἐνεπίμπλαντο κακοῖς, προκόπτοντες ἐν τοῖς αἰσχίστοις, καὶ πλεῖον ἑαυτῶν ἐπεκτείνοντες τὴν ἀσεβείαν. τοῦτο δὲ καὶ ἡ θεία γραφή μαρτύρεται λέγουσα· “Ὅταν ἔλθῃ ἀσεβῆς εἰς βάθος κακῶν, καταφρονεῖ.””

[12] Cf. Plato’s allegory of the cave in his *Republic* 514a–520a.

[13] *Ibid.*, CG 9.18 (Thomson 1971, pp. 24–25): “Τὸν ἀληθινὸν καὶ ὄντως ὄντα Θεὸν [...] ἀποστρεφόμενοι.”

[14] *Ibid.*, CG 9.1–14 (Thomson 1971, pp. 22–23): “Ἄρτι γὰρ ἀπεπήδησεν ἡ διάνοια τῶν ἀνθρώπων ἀπὸ Θεοῦ, καὶ καταβαίνοντες ταῖς ἐννοίαις καὶ τοῖς λογισμοῖς οἱ ἄνθρωποι, πρώτοις οὐρανῶ καὶ ἡλίῳ καὶ σελήνῃ καὶ τοῖς ἄστροις τὴν τοῦ Θεοῦ τιμὴν ἀνέθηκαν, ἐκείνους οὐ μόνον θεοὺς εἶναι νομίζοντες, ἀλλὰ καὶ τῶν ἄλλων τῶν μετ’ αὐτοὺς αἰτίους τυγχάνειν· εἴτ’, ἐπικαταβαίνοντες τοῖς σκοτεινοῖς λογισμοῖς, αἰθέρα καὶ τὸν ἄερα καὶ τὰ ἐν τῷ ἀέρι προσηγόρευσαν θεοὺς. προβαίνοντες δὲ τοῖς κακοῖς, ἤδη καὶ τὰ στοιχεῖα, καὶ τὰς ἀρχὰς τῆς τῶν σωμάτων συστάσεως, τὴν θερμὴν καὶ τὴν ψυχρὰν καὶ τὴν ξηρὰν καὶ τὴν ὑγρὰν οὐσίαν θεοὺς ἀνύμνησαν. ὡς δὲ οἱ τέλειον πεσόντες περὶ τὴν γῆν ἰλυσπῶνται δίκην τῶν ἐν τῇ χέρσῳ κοχλιῶν· οὕτως οἱ ἀσεβέστατοι τῶν ἀνθρώπων, πεσόντες καὶ καταπεσόντες ἀπὸ τῆς περὶ Θεοῦ φαντασίας, λοιπὸν καὶ ἀνθρώπους καὶ ἀνθρώπων μορφάς, τῶν μὲν ἔτι ζώντων, τῶν δὲ καὶ μετὰ θάνατον εἰς θεοὺς ἀνέθηκαν.”

[15] *Ibid.*, GC 19.5 (Thomson 1971, pp. 52–53).

[16] *Ibid.*, GC 19.18 (Thomson 1971, pp. 52–53).

[17] *Ibid.*, GC 19.18–21 (Thomson 1971, pp. 52–53).

[18] *Ibid.*, CG 23.38–47 (Thomson 1971, pp. 64–65; trans. slightly modified): “Ἐκπεσόντες γὰρ ἀπὸ τῆς πρὸς τὸν ἕνα Θεὸν κατανοήσεως, εἰς πολλὰ καὶ διάφορα καταπεπτώκασι· καὶ ἀποστραφέντες τὸν ἀληθῶς τοῦ Πατρὸς Λόγον, τὸν πάντων Σωτῆρα Χριστόν, εἰκότως εἰς πολλὰ τὴν διάνοιαν ἔχουσι ῥεμβομένην. καὶ ὥσπερ οἱ τὸν ἥλιον ἀποστραφέντες καὶ ἐν σκοτεινοῖς

γενόμενοι τόποις, πολλὰς ἀνόδους κυκλεύουσιν ὁδοὺς, καὶ τοὺς μὲν παρόντας οὐχ ὀρῶσι, τοὺς δὲ μὴ ὄντας φαντάζονται ὡς παρόντας, καὶ “βλέποντες οὐ βλέπουσι.” τὸν αὐτὸν τρόπον οἱ τὸν Θεὸν ἀποστραφέντες καὶ σκοτισθέντες τὴν ψυχὴν ῥεμβόμενον ἔχουσι τὸν νοῦν, καὶ τὰ οὐκ ὄντα ὡς μεθύοντες καὶ μὴ ὀρῶντες φαντάζονται.’

[19] For example, Louth believes that the double treatise presents two different views of salvation and suggests that Athanasius went through a career from a young Origenist in *Contra Gentes* to an independent thinker in *De Incarnatione*. See Louth 1975, p. 227; cf. *Ibid.*, pp. 1981, 77–80. For more views, see Pettersen 1990, pp. 14–20; Widdicombe 1994, pp. 147–8; Robertson 2007, pp. 148–151; Stead 1988, pp. 229–242; Haarlem 1961, p. 58; Roldanus 1968, pp. 11–123.

[20] For example, Pettersen remarks that “while there are different emphases in the *Contra Gentes* and the *De Incarnatione*, there are not different conceptions of mankind’s redemption.” [1] See Pettersen 1990, p. 16. Cf. Anatolios 2004, p. 31, who makes a similar statement arguing that the variance in Athanasius’ works has to do with a difference in emphases: “He [Athanasius] maintains a remarkable consistency in his theological vision and even vocabulary, albeit with some notable developments and variance of emphases.” Meijering argues for the consistency of Athanasian thought based on the apologetic structure of the treatise and its four different means (or “die Wege”) of the restoration of humanity: “Als der Mensch über diese drei Wege [i.e., the soul, creation, and Scriptures] die Gotteserkenntnis nicht erlangen konnte, erschien das Wort, das ihn im Anfang erschuf, in einem menschlichen Körper, um so das Bild Gottes und damit die Gotteserkenntnis im Menschen zu erneuern [...] Somit stellt sich der globale Aufbau des Doppelwerkes so dar, als dass von den vier Wegen der Gottesoffenbarung drei in CG behandelt werden und der vierte in DI. In den Hauptsachen kann sich keine Veränderung in den Ansichten des

Athanasius vollzogen haben, etwa in dem Sinne, dass in CG den Heiden aufgrund einer 'natürlichen Theologie' weiter entgegen käme als in DI, das 'christozentrische Theologie' bietet. Die Feststellung in DI 12, dass der Mensch über die ersten drei Wege Gotteserkenntnis hätte erlangen können, er sie aber wegen seiner Sünde eben faktisch nicht erlangte, war auch bereits in CG getroffen worden." See Meijering 1991, p. 316.

[21] Ibid., GC 33.22–26 (Thomson 1971, pp. 90–91): "Ἀλλὰ πολλάκις, ἐπὶ κλίνης τούτου κειμένου καὶ μὴ κινουμένου, ἀλλ' ὡς ἐν θανάτῳ κοιμωμένου, αὕτη κατὰ τὴν ἑαυτῆς δύναμιν γρηγορεῖ, καὶ ὑπερεκβαίνει τὴν τοῦ σώματος φύσιν· καὶ ὡσπερ ἀποδημοῦσα τούτου, μένουσα ἐν τῷ σώματι, τὰ ὑπὲρ γῆν φαντάζεται καὶ θεωρεῖ, πολλάκις δὲ καὶ τοῖς ἔξω τῶν γηγίνων σωμάτων ἀγίοις καὶ ἀγγέλοις συναντᾷ."

[22] Ibid., CG 34.1–3 (Thomson 1971, pp. 92–93): "They have denied God for the worship of inanimate beings, so they do not think they have a rational soul" (ὡσπερ τὸν Θεὸν ἠρνήσαντο καὶ ἄψυχα θρησκευοῦσιν, οὕτω καὶ ψυχὴν οὐκ ἔχειν λογικὴν νομίζοντες).

[23] Ibid., CG 34.7–8 (Thomson 1971, pp. 92–93): Ὡς μὴ ἔχοντες ψυχὴν παρὰ λόγον τολμῶσι.

[24] Ibid., CG 34.12–19 (Thomson 1971, pp. 92–93): "Δύνανται γάρ, ὡσπερ ἀπεστράφησαν τῇ διανοίᾳ τὸν Θεὸν καὶ τὰ οὐκ ὄντα ἀνεπλάσαντο εἰς θεοὺς, οὕτως ἀναβῆναι τῷ νῷ τῆς ψυχῆς, καὶ πάλιν ἐπιστρέψαι πρὸς τὸν Θεόν. ἐπιστρέψαι δὲ δύνανται, ἐὰν ὃν ἐνεδύσαντο ῥύπον πάσης ἐπιθυμίας ἀπόθωνται, καὶ τοσοῦτον ἀπονίψωνται, ἕως ἂν ἀπόθωνται πᾶν τὸ συμβεβηκὸς ἀλλότριον τῇ ψυχῇ, καὶ μόνην αὐτὴν ὡσπερ γέγονεν ἀποδείξωσιν, ἴν' οὕτως ἐν αὐτῇ θεωρῆσαι τὸν τοῦ Πατρὸς Λόγον, καθ' ὃν καὶ γεγόνασιν ἐξ ἀρχῆς, δυνηθῶσι."

[25] Ibid., CG 34.27–31 (Thomson 1971, pp. 92–93): "Ἡ εἰ μὴ αὐτάρκης ἐστὶν ἢ παρὰ τῆς ψυχῆς διδασκαλία διὰ τὰ ἐπιθολοῦντα ταύτης ἔξωθεν τὸν νοῦν, καὶ μὴ ὄραν αὐτὴν τὸ κρεῖττον· ἀλλ' ἔστι πάλιν καὶ ἀπὸ τῶν φαινομένων τὴν περὶ τοῦ

Θεοῦ γινῶσιν καταλαβεῖν, τῆς κτίσεως ὡσπερ γράμμασι διὰ τῆς τάξεως καὶ ἁρμονίας τὸν ἑαυτῆς δεσπότην καὶ ποιητὴν σημαινούσης καὶ βοώσης."

[26] Ibid., CG 38.30 (Thomson 1971, pp. 104–105).

[27] Ibid., CG 38.22–23 (Thomson 1971, pp. 104–105): "Οὕτως ἐν τῇ τοῦ παντὸς."

[28] Ibid., CG 39.27 (Thomson 1971, pp. 108–109): "Διαφόρους εἶχε καὶ τὰς κινήσεις καὶ ἀνομοίους ἑαυτῷ."

[29] Ibid., CG 39.29–30 (Thomson 1971, pp. 108–109): "Πάλιν ἦν ἀκοσμία καὶ τοῦ παντὸς ἀταξία."

[30] Ibid., CG 45.1–4 (Thomson 1971, pp. 122–123): "Ὡσπερ γάρ, ἀναβλέψαντας εἰς τὸν οὐρανὸν καὶ ἰδόντας τὸν κόσμον αὐτοῦ καὶ τὸ τῶν ἄστρον φῶς, ἔστιν ἐνθυμεῖσθαι τὸν ταῦτα διακοσμοῦντα Λόγον· οὕτω νοοῦντας Λόγον Θεοῦ, νοεῖν ἐστὶν ἀνάγκη καὶ τὸν τούτου Πατέρα Θεόν, ἐξ οὗ προῖων εἰκότως τοῦ ἑαυτοῦ Πατρὸς ἐρμηνεῦς καὶ ἄγγελος λέγεται."

[31] Ibid., CG 41.11 (Thomson 1971, pp. 112–113).

[32] Ibid., CG 41.11–12 (Thomson 1971, pp. 112–113): "Ῥευστή τις καὶ ἀσθενής καὶ θνητὴ καθ' ἑαυτὴν συγκρινομένη τυγχάνει."

[33] Ibid., CG 45.12 (Thomson 1971, pp. 124–123)

[34] Ibid., CG 45.36–44 (Thomson 1971, pp. 124–123): "Ὁ γὰρ Ἰουδαίων πάλαι λαὸς κατὰ πλεῖον εἶχε τὴν διδασκαλίαν, ὅτι μὴ μόνον ἐκ τῶν τῆς κτίσεως ἔργων, ἀλλὰ καὶ ἐκ τῶν θείων γραφῶν εἶχον τὴν περὶ Θεοῦ γινῶσιν. καὶ καθόλου δὲ τοὺς ἀνθρώπους ἀπὸ τῆς περὶ τὰ εἰδῶλα πλάνης καὶ ἀλόγου φαντασίας ἀφέλκων, φησὶν· "Οὐκ ἔσονταί σοι θεοὶ ἕτεροι πλὴν ἐμοῦ." οὐχ ὡς ὄντων δὲ θεῶν ἄλλων κωλύει τούτους αὐτοὺς ἔχειν, ἀλλ' ἵνα μή τις, τὸν ἀληθινὸν ἀποστραφεὶς Θεόν, ἑαυτῷ τὰ μὴ ὄντα θεοποιεῖν ἄρξηται, ὁποῖοί εἰσιν οἱ παρὰ ποιηταῖς καὶ συγγραφεῦσιν ὀνομασθέντες καὶ δειχθέντες οὐκ ὄντες θεοί."

[35] Athanasius, *De Inc.* 14.13–15 (Thomson 1971, pp. 166, trans. mine): "Ἐπειδὴ δὲ καὶ

είδωλομανία καὶ ἀθεότης κατεῖχε τὴν οἰκουμένην καὶ ἡ περὶ Θεοῦ γνῶσις ἐκέκρυπτο, τίνος ἦν διδάξαι τὴν οἰκουμένην περὶ Πατρός;

[36] *Ibid.*, *De Inc.* 14.33–40 (Thomson 1971, pp. 168–169): "Οὐχί γε· παρεῖδον γὰρ τοῦτο πρότερον οἱ ἄνθρωποι, καὶ οὐκέτι μὲν ἄνω, κάτω δὲ τοὺς ὀφθαλμοὺς ἐσχήκασιν. Ὅθεν εἰκότως ἄνθρωπος θέλων ὠφελεῖσθαι, ὡς ἄνθρωπος ἐπιδημεῖ, λαμβάνων ἑαυτῷ σῶμα ὅμοιον ἐκείνοις, καὶ ἐκ τῶν κάτω – λέγω δὴ διὰ τῶν τοῦ σώματος ἔργων – ἵνα οἱ μὴ θελήσαντες αὐτὸν γνῶναι ἐκ τῆς εἰς τὰ ὅλα προνοίας καὶ ἡγεμονίας αὐτοῦ, κὰν ἐκ τῶν δι' αὐτοῦ τοῦ σώματος ἔργων γνῶσονται τὸν ἐν τῷ σώματι τοῦ Θεοῦ Λόγον, καὶ δι' αὐτοῦ τὸν Πατέρα."

[37] *Ibid.*, *De Inc.* 35.16–17 (Thomson 1971, pp. 218–219): Τῆ τοῦ Σωτῆρος ἐπιδημίᾳ καὶ πάντα τὰ ἔθνη πανταχόθεν ἐπιγινώσκειν τὸν Θεὸν ἤρξαντο.

[38] *Ibid.*, *De Inc.* 15.25–37 (Thomson 1971, pp. 170–173): "Εἰ δὲ καὶ εἰς δαίμονας ἦσαν προληφθέντες, ἀλλ' ὀρῶντες αὐτοὺς διωκομένους ὑπὸ τοῦ Κυρίου, ἐγίνωσκον μόνον εἶναι τοῦτον τὸν τοῦ Θεοῦ Λόγον, καὶ οὐκ εἶναι θεοὺς τοὺς δαίμονας. Εἰ δὲ καὶ εἰς νεκροὺς ἤδη τούτων ἦν ὁ νοῦς κατασχεθεῖς, ὥστε θρησκεύειν ἡρώας, καὶ τοὺς παρὰ ποιηταῖς λεγομένους θεοὺς· ἀλλ' ὀρῶντες τὴν τοῦ Σωτῆρος ἀνάστασιν, ὠμολόγουν ἐκείνους εἶναι ψευδεῖς, καὶ μόνον τὸν Κύριον ἀληθινόν, τὸν τοῦ Πατρὸς Λόγον, τὸν καὶ τοῦ θανάτου κυριεύοντα. Διὰ τοῦτο καὶ γεγέννηται, καὶ ἄνθρωπος ἐφάνη, καὶ ἀπέθανε, καὶ ἀνέστη, ἀμβλύνας καὶ ἐπισκιάσας τὰ τῶν πῶποτε γενομένων ἀνθρώπων διὰ τῶν ἰδίων ἔργων, ἵνα ὅπου δ' ἂν ᾧσι προληφθέντες οἱ ἄνθρωποι, ἐκεῖθεν αὐτοὺς ἀναγάγη, καὶ διδάξῃ τὸν ἀληθινὸν ἑαυτοῦ Πατέρα, καθάπερ καὶ αὐτὸς φησιν· "Ἦλθον σῶσαι καὶ εὐρεῖν τὸ ἀπολωλός."

[39] *Ibid.*, *De Inc.* 25.17–39 (Thomson 1971, pp. 194–196): "Καὶ πάλιν εἰ ὁ ἐχθρὸς τοῦ γένους ἡμῶν διάβολος, ἐκπεσὼν ἀπὸ τοῦ οὐρανοῦ, περὶ τὸν ἀέρα τὸν ὧδε κάτω πλανᾶται, κάκεῖ τῶν σὺν αὐτῷ δαιμόνων ὡς ὁμοίων ἐν τῇ ἀπειθείᾳ

ἐξουσιάζων, φαντασίας μὲν δι' αὐτῶν ἐνεργεῖ τοῖς ἀπατωμένοις, ἐπιχειρεῖ δὲ τοῖς ἀνερχομένοις ἐμποδίζειν· καὶ περὶ τούτου φησὶν ὁ Ἀπόστολος· "Κατὰ τὸν ἄρχοντα τῆς ἐξουσίας τοῦ ἀέρος, τοῦ νῦν ἐνεργοῦντος ἐν τοῖς υἱοῖς τῆς ἀπειθείας," ἦλθε δὲ ὁ Κύριος ἵνα τὸν μὲν διάβολον καταβάλλῃ, τὸν δὲ ἀέρα καθαρίσῃ, καὶ ὁδοποιήσῃ ἡμῖν τὴν εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον, ὡς εἶπεν ὁ Ἀπόστολος, "διὰ τοῦ καταπετάσματος, τοῦτ' ἔστιν τῆς σαρκὸς αὐτοῦ," τοῦτο δὲ ἔδει γενέσθαι διὰ τοῦ θανάτου· ποίῳ δ' ἂν ἄλλῳ θανάτῳ ἐγεγόνει ταῦτα, ἢ τῷ ἐν ἀέρι γενομένῳ, φημί δὴ τῷ σταυρῷ; Μόνος γὰρ ἐν τῷ ἀέρι τις ἀποθνήσκει, ὁ σταυρῷ τελειούμενος. Διὸ καὶ εἰκότως τοῦτον ὑπέμεινε ὁ Κύριος. Οὕτω γὰρ ὑψωθεῖς, τὸν μὲν ἀέρα ἐκαθάριζεν ἀπὸ τε τῆς διαβολικῆς καὶ πάσης τῶν δαιμόνων ἐπιβουλῆς λέγων· "Ἐθεώρουν τὸν Σατανᾶν ὡς ἀστραπὴν πεσόντα," τὴν εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον ὁδοποιῶν ἐνεκαίνιζε λέγων πάλιν· "Ἄρατε πύλας οἱ ἄρχοντες ὑμῶν καὶ ἐπάρθητε πύλαι αἰώνιοι." Οὐ γὰρ αὐτὸς ὁ Λόγος ἦν ὁ χρήζων ἀνοιξεως τῶν πυλῶν, πάντων Κύριος ὢν, οὐδὲ κεκλεισμένον ἦν τι τῶν ποιημάτων τῷ ποιητῇ, ἀλλ' ἡμεῖς ἦμεν οἱ χρήζοντες, οὓς ἀνέφερεν αὐτὸς διὰ τοῦ ἰδίου σώματος αὐτοῦ. Ὡς γὰρ ὑπὲρ πάντων αὐτὸ προσήνεγκε τῷ θανάτῳ, οὕτως δι' αὐτοῦ πάλιν ὠδοποίησε τὴν εἰς οὐρανοὺς ἄνοδον."

[40] Athanasius spends a great deal of time reflecting on how the effectiveness of grace and security of salvation is ensured by the fact that the work of salvation is located within the Savior himself, who does what humanity cannot accomplish on its own. For an analysis of this aspect, see Lytvynenko 2021, pp. 128, 135–137.

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